

A Structured Equation Modeling Approach towards Brand Loyalty

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Abstract

Purpose

The purpose of this study is to understand the factors influencing brand loyalty of consumers through structural equation modeling approach. The other purpose of this study is to understand the degree of relationship between independent and dependent variables.

Methodology

The data for the study is collected through 150 consumers of FMCG products in Chennai city. IBM SPSS 22 version software and AMOS is used to process and analyze the collected data for the study. To achieve the stated research objective, structural equation modeling has been used to understand the complex relationship between dependent and independent variables.

Findings

The study identifies that brand affect has a significant impact on brand relevance. These are discussed in detail at results and discussion section.

Implications

The results of the study indicate that the proposed model best represent the brand loyalty of customers by satisfying model fit criteria. Thus this model can be further improved for researches seeking to understand brand loyalty among customers.

Keywords: Brand Affect, Brand Image, Brand Relevance, Brand Performance, Brand Trust, Structural Equation Modeling.

Introduction

Branding has appeared as a more current orientation that provides marketers with that stability of creativity, innovation and knowledge with experiences. Branding has emerged as a prime tool used to differentiate a company's products from the rival's products. Branding has three main purposes: product identification and differentiation (brand), repeat sales (loyalty) and product development by considering customers level of expectation. Companies in the last decade have recognized the significance of branding on these three levels and have uncovered the advantages of retaining customers rather than looking for new ones. In this regard, companies and business enterprises have recognized the significance of brand loyalty. The concept of brand loyalty first emerged as a uni-dimensional construct. In the 1950s, two separate loyalty concepts were developed. Both the loyalty concepts use to measure attitude and behaviour. The bi-dimensional composite model presented by Jacoby and Chestnut in 1971 united both the attitudinal and

behavioural construct signalling the beginning of much concern in brand loyalty research. From the 1990s, the concept brand loyalty became one of the most researched topics within the field of service marketing. Since 2001, brand loyalty has grown in spite of the nonstop entry of new products entering the market. This trend can be accelerated to the consumer becoming aware of the benefits of well known brands, like the advantage of saving time searching for products. Indeed, brand loyalty is constructed over time through a collection of positive experiences that requires continuous effort and concentration to detail. Loyal customers are repeat customers who choose a company's brand without even considering other alternatives. They buy more and regularly and also they frequently recommend as well as advice about a brand to others. The American Marketing Association defines brand loyalty as "the situation in which a consumer generally buys the same manufacturer-originated product or service repeatedly over time rather than buying from multiple suppliers within the category" or "the degree to which a consumer consistently purchases the same brand within a product class". Brand Loyalty plays a significant role in the success of marketing efforts of the company. With this background on brand loyalty, this research paper seeks to build a structural model using brand trust as measuring variable of brand loyalty and brand performance, brand affect, brand relevance, brand image as independent variables.

Review of Literature

Androulidakis ; G. Kandus (2011) correlated the brand of mobile phone to users' security practices,. Users show different behavior in an array of characteristics, according to the brand of the mobile phone they are using. As such, there is a categorization of areas, different for each brand, where users are clearly lacking security mind, possibly due to lack of awareness. Such a categorization can help phone manufacturers enhance their mobile phones in regards to security, preferably transparently for the user.

SanySanuriMohd.Mokhtar; Ahmed AuduMaiyaki ; NorzainibtMohd Noor (2011) explores the relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction on customer loyalty with regards to mobile phone usage among the postgraduate students of a university in Northern Malaysia. The results show that both service quality and customer satisfaction significantly affect the level of customer loyalty of mobile phone users in Malaysia. It was therefore, recommended that mobile service providers should pay special attention to their service quality and the factors that drive customer satisfaction.

TajzadehNamin A. A. RahmaniVahid ;TajzadehNaminAidin (2012) analysed that the process of deciding over (choosing) a brand may be influenced by situation and content. The findings suggest a significant relationship between the variables "brand attitude", "corporate attitude", and "product (cell phone) choice". In addition, no significant relationship was found between individual decision making processes (independent or mediated) and product choice.

Nasr Azad ; Maryam Safaei (2012)states that there are many evidences to believe that customers select their products based on brand name. Products also maintain their own characteristics, which make them differentiable from others. In this paper, researchers have present an empirical study to determine important factors influencing customers' purchasing intend for cellular phones in capital city of Iran, Tehran. The results of the study show that there are some positive relationships between exclusive name and quality perception, between exclusive name and word of mouth advertisement, between quality perception and fidelity, between word of mouth advertisement and brand name and between brand name image and brand name.

ArvindSahay and Nivedita Sharma (2010) focused on brand relationships are indeed important for different categories of young consumers; second, to investigate the effect of peer influence, family influence, and brand relationships on switching intentions amongst young consumers;

and third, to look at the impact of price changes on switching intentions in the context of brand relationships. Researcher's results suggest that young consumers develop relationships on all brand relationship dimensions

Shibashish, Chakraborty and KalyanSengupta (2008) endeavors to make a detailed study on important demographic variables of customers affecting brand switching of customers. This study will highlight pertinent aspects of prediction of switching proclivity of customers from one service provider to another.

Statement of the Problem

Brand loyalty has been becoming increasing area of study in recent years. Though the many researches are carried out in this area, the recent studies are focusing on developing a model that will reflect the brand loyalty of customers towards the products available in the market. Changing business environment and increasing competition forced customers to look into various factors in order to become loyal to the particular brand. This necessitates the need to study the brand loyalty and develop a model that affects the brand loyalty of customers.

Novelty of the Research

The novelty of the research states the originality of the research. In other words, it states in what way this research is unique from related researches in the topic under study. While there are various research studies focused on using structured equation model in studying the brand loyalty this research study is also unique like the related studies relating to brand loyalty because it considers some new variables like brand affect, brand relevance to study the brand loyalty of customers.

Objective of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows

- To study whether brand affect has a significant impact on brand relevance.
- To identify whether brand image has a significant impact on the brand relevance.
- To identify whether brand relevance has impact on the brand performance of the customers.
- To identify whether brand performance of the customers is affected by brand trust.

Scope of the Study

The Study titled "A Structured Equation Modeling Approach towards brand loyalty" is limited to the respondents in Chennai city. While there are various factors affecting brand loyalty in organization, the study considers only factors like brand image, brand performance, brand trust, brand relevance and brand affect with some of the listed factors being loaded within other major factors identified by the study.

Significance of the Study

The study seeks to benefit the following categories of people

Marketing researchers

The results arrived by the study will provide an insight to the marketing researchers to consider some new variables to study the brand loyalty of customers towards the products of a particular firm. Further it will also provide them new ideas on developing a further more advanced model to study the brand loyalty of customers and the results can further contribute to the literature if the study is conducted by changing the conditions under which this study was carried out.

FMCG Companies

Though this study focuses on Patanjali products, this study will benefit other FMCG companies also. It will provide them an about the factors affecting the brand switchover decision of the consumers and will give them an idea about the areas to be focused by the companies for better attraction and retention of customers and making them loyal to their concerned brands.

Research Methodology

Type of Research

This research study is a quantitative research study. A quantitative research study is a study where a problem which is being studied by the researcher is supported by generating data which can be later converted into usable statistics giving meaningful conclusion.

Sources of Data

Primary Data

Primary sources are the sources that are collected originally rather than being already made available. The data obtained from these sources are called primary data. The primary data for the study is collected through survey method using structured questionnaire. The primary data often is available in raw form which is then processed to make itself suitable for further analysis to arrive at meaningful conclusion.

Sampling Design

Sample Size: The sample size for the study is 150 respondents from Chennai city. The sample size for the study is arrived through G-power statistics 3.1 software which helps in determining the sample size based on the analytical tool used for the study.

Sampling Technique: This research study is based on simple random sampling method. This sampling technique gives each element an equal and independence chance of being selected rather than pre-determining the samples to be selected.

Sampling Unit: The sampling unit for the study is the consumers of FMCG products. Industrial consumers do not represent the sampling unit for the study.

Statistical Design

The analysis for this study has been carried out through IBM SPSS Version 22 Software. The analytical tool used for the study is structural equation model analysis. Structural Equation Modeling is a multivariate statistical analysis technique that is used to analyze structural relationships between the variables used in the study. This technique is the combination of factor analysis and multiple regression analysis, and it is used to analyze the structural relationship between measured variables and latent constructs. The aim of the technique is to provide a quantitative test for hypothesized model proposed by the researcher.

Instrumental Reliability

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of items
0.835	35

The above table shows the reliability analysis of the variables used in the study. A Cronbach Alpha of more than 0.5 is acceptable however it is 0.835 in case of the present study which indicate a high level of reliability

Limitations of the Study

The various limitations of the study are as follows

- The study uses the data collected from both primary and secondary data. Therefore limitations of these sources apply to this study.
- The study deals with the data made available and therefore it may not judge the entire scenario.
- The study is mainly focused on customers in Chennai city and therefore results can vary when the same study is conducted in any other geographical locations

Results and Discussions

Figure 1 Shows the Structural Equation Model

Interpretation

The figure 1 shows the structural equation model toward brand loyalty after performing confirmatory factor analysis. The model consist of five variables out of which two variables namely brand affect and brand image are latent variables that is nothing but independent variables while brand relevance, brand performance and brand trust are observed variables or dependent variables.

**Table 1 Shows Unstandardized Co-efficients
Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)**

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
BI4	<---	BI	1.000				
BI3	<---	BI	.964	.067	14.405	***	
BI1	<---	BI	.713	.066	10.799	***	
BP5	<---	BP	1.652	.181	9.155	***	
BP4	<---	BP	1.000				
BP3	<---	BP	.651	.127	5.135	***	
BP1	<---	BP	.607	.126	4.820	***	
BR2	<---	BR	1.283	.103	12.408	***	
BR1	<---	BR	1.000				
BA5	<---	BA	1.000				
BA4	<---	BA	.942	.066	14.208	***	

BA3	<---	BA	.876	.056	15.750	***	
BA2	<---	BA	.829	.063	13.181	***	
BT4	<---	BT	1.190	.105	11.333	***	
BT3	<---	BT	1.159	.103	11.277	***	
BT2	<---	BT	1.000				
BT1	<---	BT	.992	.092	10.836	***	

Interpretation

The above table 1 shows the results of unstandardized regression co-efficients. The unstandardized regression co-efficients helps in measuring the effects of every metric unit of change in independent variable on the dependent variable. However in the above table the co-efficients between sub variables of the observed and latent variables is shown. Generally a regression estimate of above 0.5 is considered good. Since in the above table all the values are above 0.5, the model has a good fit.

**Table 2 shows the Standardized Regression Co-efficients
Standardized Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)**

			Estimate
BI4	<---	BI	.854
BI3	<---	BI	.902
BI1	<---	BI	.696
BP5	<---	BP	.937
BP4	<---	BP	.604
BP3	<---	BP	.404
BP1	<---	BP	.376
BR2	<---	BR	.884
BR1	<---	BR	.764
BA5	<---	BA	.899
BA4	<---	BA	.799
BA3	<---	BA	.859
BA2	<---	BA	.778
BT4	<---	BT	.796
BT3	<---	BT	.792
BT2	<---	BT	.792
BT1	<---	BT	.762

Interpretation

The table 2 shows the results of the standardized regression co-efficients. The Standardized Regression Co-efficients changes in accordance with changes in the standard deviation. It is useful in comparing the relative strengths of the co-efficients. Generally, the closer the value of SRC to 1, greater is the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable. Similarly, closer the value of SRC to 0, weaker is the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable. Except the relationship between sub variables 3 and 1 of brand performance all other variables proves to be good for the model..

Table 3 shows the model fit indices

Model Fit Indices	Results	Suggested Results
Chi square/Degree of freedom	1.280	≤ 5.00 (Hair et al., 1998)
GFI	0.930	>0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
CFI	0.984	>0.90 (Hair et al. 2006)
AGFI	0.900	>0.90 (Daire et al., 2008)
NFI	0.931	≥0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
IFI	0.979	>0.90(Hair et al. 2006)
TLI	0.984	>0.90 (Hair et al., 1998)
RMSEA	0.038	<0.08 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)

Interpretation

The above table 3 shows the model fit criteria which the proposed model is expected to satisfy. The actual results along with the suggested results by the various literatures are presented in the above table.

The Chisquare values are obtained through maximum likelihood estimates. The maximum likelihood estimates are considered to be unbiased, consistent measure and satisfies the multivariate assumptions. A researcher is normally interested in obtaining the non significant chisquare value as it represents that the implied theoretical model represents the significant sample variance – covariance relationships in the matrices. Therefore, chisquare is considered at the measure of badness of fit. According to Hair et al.,(1998), chisquare in relation to the degrees of freedom should be less than or equal to 5, thereby the model satisfies this condition also.

Goodness of Fit Index(GFI) measures the of variance and co-variance that is predicted by the reproduce matrices. According to Hu and Bentler 1999, the GFI value should of 0.90 and above is acceptable. Since the computed amount value is 0.93, the proposed model has a good fit .

Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) is normally adjusted for the degrees of freedom of a model to a relative number of variables used in the model. Both GFI and AGFI are used to compare the model fit of the different models with same data or same model with different data sets. According to literature, the suggested value for AGFI is 0.90. Since the calculated value is 0.90 we conclude that the model has a good fit.

Normed Fit Index (NFI) is used to compare the restricted model with a full model using a baseline null model. According to Hu and Bentler 1999, the suggested value should be greater than or equal to 0.90. Since the computed value 0.931 is greater than the required value, the model has a good fit.

Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) is the model comparison index which is used to compare the alternative models or compare the proposed model with the null model. According to Hair et.al , the suggested value for TLI should greater than or equal to 0.90. Since the computed TLI is 0.984 which is greater than the suggested value, the model has a good fit.

Root Mean Square Error of approximation(RMSEA) is a similar measure like non significant chisquare test discussed earlier. There is a relationship between these two measures. When a non significant chisquare is obtained, the RMSEA also seems to fall within the range of acceptable fit. According to Hair.et.al (2006), RMSEA should be less than 0.08, The calculated RMSEA 0.038 is less than the 0.08, thereby satisfying the condition laid out by the relevant literatures.

The Comparative Fit Index(CFI) measure the improvements in noncolinearity in moving from the initial model to the modified model According to Hair et.al (2006), a CFI value of more than

0.90 is acceptable. Since the calculated value which is 0.984 is more than the acceptable value, it is clear that the model has a good fit.

Table 5 Shows the Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
BR	<---	BA	.415	.082	5.062	***
BR	<---	BI	.301	.068	4.389	***
BP	<---	BR	.807	.102	7.933	***
BT	<---	BP	.036	.078	.470	.639

Interpretation

The table 5 shows the results of the unstandardized regression co-efficient which used to test the significance of the proposed paths by the model. Each path is stated as one hypothesis and preceded accordingly.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between Brand Affect and Brand Relevance.

The Critical Ratio is obtained by dividing parameter estimate by standard error. The Critical Ratios are required to be above 1.96 for statistical Significance. Here, the calculated value is more than the required value and is reflected by the p-value significance. Hence it can be concluded that brand affect has a significant influence on the brand relevance.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between Brand Image and Brand Relevance.

The Critical ratio 4.389 is greater than 1.96 and the p-value is highly significant at 1% level. Since the calculated value is less than the significance value, it can be concluded that brand image has a significant effect on the brand relevance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between Brand Relevance and Brand Performance

Since the calculated p-value is less than the significance value, it can be concluded that the brand relevance has a significant impact on the brand performance. The Critical Ratio 7.933 is also above the required value of 1.96 for statistical significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between Brand Performance and Brand Trust

Since the calculated p-value 0.639 is greater than the significance value at 5% level, it can be concluded that brand performance do not have a impact on brand trust. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. This is supported by the critical value of 0.470 which is less than 1.96 required for statistical significance.

Conclusion

To conclude, brand loyalty is crucial for all the FMCG companies. This is because customers are kings. The loyal customers are assets of the companies. This is because they not only contribute to the sales of the company, but through positive word of mouth brings new customers. But creating loyal customers towards a particular brand is not an easy task. The company must constantly engage in changing behavior of customers towards different brands in the market and adapt themselves to the market. Finally, the study enabled to get a practical touch with aspects of brand loyalty and structured equation model technique and understand the importance of brand loyalties to the companies.

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